

Talking about interactions: Eliciting structured interaction stories in enduring product experiences

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Abstract

In this paper, we first address the problems of assessing full sequences of interaction episodes that lead to/are followed by enduring product experiences. Enduring product experiences are dynamic experiences that occur towards the same object, in person-product relationships, through a (relatively) long period of time. The appraisal of these sequences of interaction episodes allows the assessment of information that is envisioned to be valuable to designers who are concerned with designing for experiences.

To aid the assessment of interactions linked to enduring experiences, we propose the development of a manageable tool, envisioned to (1) sensitize (inform) participants in research about interactions that may be associated with product experiences, (2) impose a structure to stories in order to (a) easily identify interactions, (b) avoid unneeded data and (c) facilitate the systematic assessment of interactions and experiences.

Here, through a succession of iterative exploratory studies, we present the first three phases of the development of the Experience Interaction Tool (EXIT).

Conference theme: Usage & Interaction

Keywords: Interaction; Product Experience; Enduring Experiences

Introduction

The *pleasure* of touching the soft surface of a table top, the *desire* to own a videogame console that has just been released, the *admiration* over a silent vacuum cleaner, and the *contempt* felt when looking at a pretentious chair design: we have experiences while interacting with products. Product Experience refers to these affective experiences involved in human-product interaction. It is the “entire set of effects that is elicited by the interaction between a user and a product, including the degree to which all our senses are gratified (aesthetic experience), the meanings we attach to the product (experience of meaning), and the feelings and emotions that are elicited (emotional experience)” (Desmet & Hekkert, 2007, p. 160). Interaction between people and products is a key aspect in understanding experiences (Forlizzi and Battarbee, 2004). For long, designers have tried, often intuitively, to incorporate experiences in their designs. In order to design for experiences, designers have also been trying to “better understand the principles of how people interact with various types of artifacts, and how those interactions affect the experiences people have” (Forlizzi & Ford, 2000, p.419). In order to facilitate designers’ attempts to ‘design for experience’ and influence the experiential impact of new designs, design researchers have been investigating product experiences by examining how interactions between people and products lead to certain experiences or are followed by certain experiences. For example, Ludden (Ludden et al, 2008) investigated types of incongruence between seeing and touching products that elicits *surprise*.

In this paper we first address the problem of collecting all interactions that might be linked to product experience. At this point, we don’t know yet which interactions leads to/are followed by experiences. Later, based on the conclusions of a pre-study, we present the problem of assessing interactions that are linked, specifically, to enduring product experiences. Enduring product experiences are dynamic experiences that occur towards the same object, in person-product relationships, through a (relatively) long period of time.

The questions that arise are: how can we understand the dynamics of interactions in enduring experiences and how can we link that to the design of these experiences. In this paper, we focus on answering the first question and report the initial iterative stages of the development of a tool to be used in research with participants. With this tool, we aim to investigate which interactions take place throughout a relationship between a person and a product and their sensible ‘contribution’ to product experience. The tool is being developed through a succession of explorative studies.

The study reported here is part of a broader research about the (enduring) experience of love in person-product relationships that is currently being conducted. In that research, we investigate

the interrelatedness between person-product interactions and the experience of love that is elicited or followed by these interactions, with the aim of contributing insights for design. This paper contributes to the investigation of how this interrelation can be studied.

Problems in Assessing Interactions

The assessment of interactions that lead to/are followed by experiences can be quite laborious and, sometimes, not even viable.

Experiences are complex

Product experience is “a multi-faceted phenomenon that involves manifestations such as subjective feelings, behavioral reactions, expressive reactions, and physiological reactions” (Desmet & Hekkert, 2007, p.59). Experiences happen in ‘a scene of various dynamic aspects’ (Jääsko et al, 2004) since they are tangled together and may occur simultaneously. Even the anticipation and remembrance of experiences generate other experiences.

Experiences are difficult to grasp and its complexity does not facilitate the assessment of associated interactions.

Experiences can be of different sizes

Experiences like surprise and irritation are short-lived. They are likely to be manifested (with the same object) during a relatively short period of time in a small number of distinct interaction episodes.

On the other hand, based on earlier research, enduring experiences like love tend to last longer and change through time (Russo, Boess, and Hekkert, submitted). Like interpersonal close relationships (Kelley et al, 1983), person-product relationships are enduring experiences and can be thought of as shaped by sequences of interactions episodes (see figure 1). Interaction episodes are moments in time where a person interacts with a specific product (e.g., buying the product; using the product; cleaning the product).

Figure 1 – Hierarchy of interactions in person-product relationships

Each interaction episode that occurred in person-product relationships may contain a variable number of interactions. We assume that interactions carried out in person-product relationships (somehow) contribute to the enduring experience. Correspondingly, changes in the enduring experience occur due to changes on the ways in which people and products interact through time. We believe that, once we can assess interaction episodes (and the interactions within) that occur throughout person-product relationships, we may be able to design for enduring experiences.

Assessing Interactions Linked to Enduring Experiences

In a pre-study, we sought to assess the interaction episodes (and interactions within) that are carried out in person-product relationships that lead to/are followed by the experience of love. We have performed a pilot study with 3 participants (1 female; 2 male) and the products they love to use (a hammock, a folding bike, a laptop, respectively). The goal of the study was to collect retrospective interaction stories in order to assess interaction episodes (and the interactions within) that occurred throughout their relationship with the loved product. Each participant was interviewed 2 times and filled in a diary (one week period). In each encounter, participants were informed about the types of interaction that may elicit product experiences and were asked to report all the remembered interaction episodes referent to those types.

The types of interaction that are linked to product experience, used to inform participants, refer to the ones proposed by Desmet and Hekkert (2007). According to their classification, experiences can be elicited by physical interactions and non-physical interactions. Physical interactions can be instrumental (e.g., using, operating products) or non-instrumental. Instrumental interactions are those in which a person interacts physically with a product, like using or operating it. Non-instrumental interactions are those in which a person interacts with a product with no particular goal, like caressing or playing with it. Non-physical interactions – like fantasizing about a product or anticipating its usage – refer to those interactions where physical contact between the person and the product is absent and, sometimes, the product is not physically present when it occurs.

This attempt brought up a few problems in assessing stories and collecting interaction episodes associated with enduring experiences. First, participant's accounts of interaction stories were difficult to manage systematically. People tell stories in a way that is convenient to them and, as a result, stories can be long, complex, and chaotic. Collecting these stories result in a large amount of (useless) data that takes too long to be assessed and analyzed. Second, interactions are difficult to be identified. Because stories can be long and chaotic, many times it was hard to identify in the content of the stories the interactions carried out. Third, participants often omitted interactions when reporting stories. Participants had difficulties to distinguish what is an

interaction and omitted certain interactions. The interaction types proposed by Desmet & Hekkert (2007) did not inform participants (at practical level) about what interactions are: participants did not know what counts as an interaction and what kind of interaction episodes they should report.

For these reasons, it is difficult to assess full sequences of interaction episodes that lead to/are followed by enduring experiences and, therefore, provide information to designers who are concerned with designing for these experiences. In order to aid the assessment and analysis of person-product interaction episodes and interactions that lead to/are followed by experiences, we propose the development of a tool. The Experience Interaction Tool (EXIT) is envisioned to aid the assessment of interaction episodes to (1) sensitize (inform) participants in research about interactions, (2) impose a structure to stories in order to (a) easily identify interactions, (b) avoid unneeded data, (c) facilitate the systematic assessment of interactions, and (d) link interactions to experiences. In addition, the tool should be convenient to use (manageable). The tool is eventually expected to contribute to the assessment of experiences.

Research

Here we present the first three phases of the development of the Experience Interaction Tool. The development of the tool follows an iterative course, where the results and findings of one phase provide information to set the objectives and goals of the next one.

Phase 1 – Assessing the structure of interactions

Method

In order to impose a structure to reports of interaction and experience, our first initiative was to find out if there is a common structure of reporting interactions and experiences that could be followed. For that, we have assessed the content of the three reports of interactions associated to enduring experiences, collected in the pre-study. The goal of phase 1 was to find common characteristics between the content of the report of interaction episodes (and interactions within) of the 3 participants.

Results

The analysis revealed certain structural aspects of reports of interactions and experiences that should be taken into consideration in the development of the tool.

Structure of Reports

The report of interaction episodes (and the interactions within) followed a basic structure: a participant performs (or not) an action towards a product and/or a person and experiences

something (emotion, reward, sensorial pleasure) towards something/someone (e.g., the product, the participant, others, the interaction) because of something (reasons). For example, a participant reported an interaction episode regarding a hammock as follows: "...I sat on the hammock with my boyfriend. I was so happy that we were sitting there, because I love to be on my hammock, and I love to be with him".

Reports of interaction events referred also to the anticipation and memory of interaction events (e.g., "at that time, I remembered one day when I took the laptop to my friend's house").

Actions

When reporting interaction and experience stories, participants have used action verbs to report the actions carry out. Action verbs are a type of verb that describes an act or activity: things people can do or that can be done (e.g., to use, to clean, to move).

Reports followed the hierarchical structure of interactions and action verbs were used to report interactions in all levels of the hierarchy. For example, one of the participants reported the episode '*buying* my bike' where several interactions occurred: '*going* to the shop', '*checking* the bikes', '*choosing* for the red bike', '*paying* for the bike', and '*taking* the bike home'. Some of these interactions contained, in themselves, sequences of interactions: in "*checking* the bike", for example, participant reported to "*look* at the bike", "*rub* the leather seat", "*touch* the metal frame", and so on.

Interactants

Action verbs were employed to account for the actions taken by a person towards a product (e.g., "I carried my bike"), actions carried out by a product towards a person (e.g., "the laptop screen smacked my fingers"), and actions products carry out by themselves (e.g., "the table collapsed"). Participants rarely reported actions carried out by products towards people and towards themselves.

The subjects that carry and receive the actions were always a person (the participant), a product, or others involved in the interaction event. On certain occasions, the subjects who carried out actions towards the products were the participants together with others. Participants have also reported interaction episodes where they 'witness' actions carried out by others towards the product and vice-versa.

Discussion

The structure of interaction reports taken from participant's reports will be implemented in the tool. The structure will be imposed on participants in order to avoid unnecessary data and facilitate the systematic assessment of stories referring to interaction episodes.

According to Crawford (2005), verb thinking is “central to understanding interactivity” (p. 91) since it focuses on the actions enacted by people and any interactive system of artifacts. In order to inform participants about interactions and to make sure the report of interaction episodes is complete we focus on the action verbs used by participants to report their interaction episodes and interactions within. Because the little amount of action verbs collected from the first study, we move on to finding more action verbs that can be used to describe interactions.

Phase 2 – Collecting relevant action verbs

Following the findings from the previous phase, in order to inform participants about interaction episodes that should be reported (and the interactions within), phase two was designed to compile a list of action verbs. These action verbs must inform participants about which person-product interactions should be reported.

Collecting actions verbs

Since it was not possible to find a complete list of action verbs in the English language, the content of the 3 reports and 52 reports of interaction episodes from a previous study (Russo, Boess, and Hekkert, submitted) were analyzed. The initiative was to collect the action verbs used by participants to report person-product interactions.

The outcome of this analysis was a list of 42 action verbs. The list of 42 action verbs was considered to be very incomplete, since it did not contain several action verbs (e.g., to try, to fix, to design, to smell) that could be envisioned to describe interaction episodes and events between people and products.

In order to extend the list and improve its scope, we added four other lists of English action verbs. The lists were: a list of action verbs for writers (Rahmel, available at www.cvisual.com), two lists of action verbs for resumes, and a list of action verbs for communicators (Hart, 2004). These efforts resulted in a list of 1454 action verbs.

Distinguishing relevant action verbs

Not all the 1454 action verbs collected could be employed to describe an action carried out between people and products. For example, interactions involving verbs like to dope, to mentor, to petition or to placate could not be envisioned.

Method

In order to obtain a selection of action verbs that are relevant to report interactions between a person and a product, 3 English native speakers (1 male; 2 female) were selected to rate the

1454 action verbs compiled as relevant or not to report actions/interactions between a person and a product. The verbs that were considered 'relevant' by at least one participant were selected.

The selected verbs formed a list of 957 action verbs possibly relevant to report interactions between people and products.

Two of the three participants mentioned that many of the verbs rated as relevant to person-product context are not commonly used. Verbs such as to abide, to fondle, or to plow are not frequently used in everyday situations and would probably not be used by participants.

Therefore, to eliminate the verbs that are not part of a participant's vocabulary, 10 participants (5 male, 5 female) with an international background and a good knowledge of the English language were asked to report which of the 957 action verbs they used frequently to report interactions with products.

From the 10 participants selected, 2 participants stopped rating at an early stage and 1 participant only concluded 80% of the ratings. From all the verbs rated as being 'relevant' to a participant's vocabulary, only the ones that were rated by at least 5 participants were selected. The selected verbs were compiled into a list of 451 action verbs that are relevant to report interactions between people and products and are part of people's vocabulary.

Phase 3 – Manageable action verbs

In order to inform participants about the actions they are supposed to report, it is essential to have a manageable number of verbs. The number of action verbs collected was quite large (451 verbs) and impractical to inform participants.

To that end, the development of a taxonomy of action verbs was needed. According to Lakoff (1987), things are categorized together on the basis of what they have in common.

Categorization is a very basic process used to make sense of things: "every time we see something as a kind of a thing (...) we are categorizing" (Lakoff, 1987, p.5).

Phase three was the development of a taxonomy of action verbs. The taxonomy is expected to comprise the 451 relevant action verbs, organized in categories. The categories should be informative with respect to the verbs they contain.

Method

Through sorting techniques, the 451 relevant action verbs were categorized by the first author, 2 specialists and 1 non-specialist. The specialists were designers with experience in person-product interaction and/or product experience. They were chosen because they are more

experienced in reflecting about products than non-specialists. The non-specialist was selected in order to check if he/she would come up with different (and maybe useful) categorization criteria.

Each participant was met individually and received 451 cards, each containing the name of one relevant action verb. A brief explanation about the development of the tool was given.

Participants were first asked to check all the cards and next, carefully organize them into groups. Participants were also asked to explain their choice for a specific classification criterion and to define each category created. Later, participants were asked to try to group the cards again, using a different criterion. This procedure was expected to be repeated until the participant could not develop new criteria for grouping the actions.

For the analysis, all taxonomies of interactions created by participants and the criteria developed were compared and analyzed. The final interaction taxonomy was made based on its manageability and its expected ability to elicit reports of interaction episodes.

The outcome of this phase is a taxonomy of interactions where each category contains similar actions carried out when reporting interaction episodes and each category clearly differs from the others.

Results

Because of the number of action verbs to be categorized were extremely large, the participants considered the task to be quite laborious and time consuming. Therefore, only participant 3 have developed a second classification criterion. Participant 3 and 4 used the same criteria to develop their taxonomies, which were accounted as one. In total, 4 distinct taxonomies were created.

Taxonomy 1 – Similarity of Actions

The criterion used by the first author to categorize the verbs was the similarity between actions. Verbs were put together based on their meaning, their connotation. Accordingly, 12 categories were created, which had between 0 to 4 sub-categories (see table 1).

Each category created contained actions that were considered to be ‘alike’ and was named after their best example (the prototypical verb). Each category refers, according to the participant, to a type of action.

Category	Sub-category	Examples	Criterion
to Use	to Operate (start/stop)	to utilize, to activate	Actions that refer to the instrumental use of products.
	to Test	to experiment, to test	
to Handle	to Move	to rotate, to turn	Actions that are performed with the hands, whether it is related to changing product’s position (to move), handling it (to manipulate), and supporting it (to hold).
	to Manipulate	to handle, to touch	
	to Hold	to support, to grab	

to Sense	-	to smell, to see, to taste, to hear, and to feel, to touch	All primary actions related to the five senses.
to Do	to Make	to build, to construct	Actions in which the product is made, designed or reproduced.
	to Reproduce	to copy, to duplicate	
to Change	to Resize (reduce/expand)	to enlarge, to shorten, to stretch	Actions that refer to modifying, changing the product in terms of size or appearance.
	to Modify	to adjust, to adapt	
	to Customize	to personalize, to decorate	
to Arrange	to Accommodate	to settle, to fit	Actions referring to the arrangement of the product.
	to Position	to align, to straighten	
	to Organize	to classify, to order, to list	
to Care	to Preserve	to maintain, to save	Actions carried out in order to keep the product for longer, whether by preserving, repairing, or assisting it.
	to Repair	to recover, to polish	
	to Assist	to help, to collaborate	
to Violate	to Hit	to slap, to kick, to punch	Violent, abusive actions carried out in order to harm or not.
	to Break	to crash	
to Examine	to Analyze	to study, to check	Any action referring to the examination of products whether it refer to a visual analysis or observation or to the investigation of product characteristics and its measurement.
	to Observe	to monitor, to view	
	to Investigate	to explore, to research	
	to Evaluate	to measure, to rate	
to Concede	to Give	to donate, to award	All actions in which one gives away the product, whether it is temporarily or definitive.
	to Sell	to commercialize, to trade	
	to Abandon	to leave, to delete	
to Obtain	to Get	to capture, to retain	All actions in which one gets hold of the product or act in order to get hold of the product.
	to Find	to discover, to detect	
	to Select	to pick, to choose	
to Share	to Tell (to report, to suggest)	to recommend, to describe, to inform	Actions that are carried out together with others, whether they refer to talking about the product or showing the product.
	to Show	to indicate	

Table 1 - Taxonomy 1 – Similarity of Actions

Taxonomy 2 – Human faculties

The criteria used by participant 2 to categorize the action verbs were the human faculties involved when performing actions. First, two categories were created: *mental actions* (e.g., to think, to anticipate) and *physical actions* (e.g., to touch, to transport). Later, another category – *social actions* – was included, representing those actions that are carried out together with other people (e.g., to show, to tell).

Taxonomy 3 – Relationship Life-Cycle

The first criterion developed by participant 3 to categorize the action verbs was based on actions that are likely to occur in specific phases of product consumption life-cycle (or person-product relationships). Four categories were created.

The first category created was named *contact*. It refers to all actions that may occur in the initial phase of person-product relationships, when the person gets in touch with the product for the first time (e.g., to spot, to check) and the actions enacted in order to consume the product (e.g., to find, to investigate).

The second category was named *consumption* and it refers to all the actions that are likely to occur when the person acquires the product (e.g., to buy, to get, to receive) and consume/use it (e.g., to use, to press, to carry).

The third category created was named *avoid discard* and it refers to all actions that are expected to be carried out by a person in order to keep the product for longer, whether in order to recover it (e.g., to repair, to fix), modify it (e.g., to renew, to change), or to clean it (e.g., to maintain, to sanitize).

The fourth category was named *discard*, and it refers to all actions carried out when products are disposed, whether the disposal is voluntary (e.g., to give, to abandon) or involuntary (e.g., to lose, to break). In this category, it was also included after-life actions, which are those that can be carried out after the product is discarded (e.g., to recycle).

Taxonomy 4 – Action Sequences (size)

Participant 3 developed a second classification criterion. The second criterion was the same created by participant 4 to categorize the action verbs. Taxonomy 4 was designed based on two distinctive levels of action that occur in sequence during interaction episodes. In both categorizations, two categories were created: the main/macro actions and the secondary/micro actions. The main/macro actions are those considered to be the ones who ‘name’, who represent the intended action in interaction episodes (e.g., to repair). The secondary/micro actions are the ‘smaller’ actions that occur inside the interaction episode (e.g., to touch, to rub).

The reasoning for this categorization is that a large action holds several small actions. For example, when a person is *cleaning* (main/macro action) a table top he/she may be *looking* at the table top, *touching*, *rubbing*, and even *caressing* (secondary/micro) it.

Discussion

Here, the relevance of the taxonomies created is discussed based on its expected ability to inform participants about actions/interactions that can be carried out when experiencing products.

Taxonomy 1 classifies action verbs based on their similarity in meaning (how verbs refer to similar actions). Each category contains similar actions that were tagged by a prototypical verb. The 12 category names in this taxonomy appear to be quite informative, since they deal with types of interaction that may be carried out with products.

This taxonomy was considered very relevant to inform about actions that are carried out in interaction episodes.

Taxonomy 2 classifies action verbs based on human faculties. This categorization is quite similar to the one proposed by Desmet & Hekkert (2007). The criteria used by the participant to classify the action verbs were considered inconsistent, since they changed throughout the classification process. First, the participant classified action verbs in terms of 'mental actions' and 'physical actions'. Later, the category 'social actions', was included, referring to actions that are carried out together or in the presence of others, whether the action was mental or physical.

Besides the fact that each category contained actions that are very different from each other, the number of actions in each category was quite high, which wouldn't facilitate its use to inform participants and collect interaction episodes through time.

Another problem is that the categories created are non-exclusive of each other. For example, '*to borrow*' is a social action, since it is an action between two people. However, it is also physical, since physical interactions occur when one is borrowing a product to another.

Taxonomy 3 classifies action verbs based on the possible stages of a person-product relationship. This categorization was considered problematic for two main reasons: first, it is based on a prediction of which interactions contribute to person-product relationship development and change. But at this point, we don't know which interactions are carried out in which relationship stage.

It is not possible to affirm at this point that certain interactions occur more frequently (or even exclusively) in person-product relationship.

Second, by trying to predict that certain actions occur only in specific periods of time, this classification forced certain 'everyday' actions such as *to touch*, *to move*, and *to see* as likely to occur in one particular phase of the relationship.

Taxonomy 4 was created based on the size of actions. This taxonomy is quite relevant in the sense that it makes a distinction between actions and interactions: the main/macro actions refer to interaction episodes and the secondary/micro actions refer to the interactions within interaction episodes.

This distinction follows the hierarchical structure of interaction episodes, highlighted by the results of the first phase of the development of the tool. This hierarchical structure is vital to the assessment of interactions since it distinguishes the actions that occur within the interactions, in interaction episodes.

The names ‘main’ and ‘secondary’ actions, given by participant 4 were not considered to be very instructive. For example, one may consider that *to touch* is a ‘main’ interaction if all he/she performed with a product in an interaction episode was *touching the product*, and not a ‘secondary’ interaction as proposed by participant 4. Therefore, decision was made to use macro and micro as categories, as proposed by participant 3.

Taxonomies 1 and 4 were considered valuable to sensitize participants with types of interactions that can be carried out with products (taxonomy 1) and structuring their report of interaction episodes by discriminating the size of interactions/actions (taxonomy 4). These two taxonomies can be merged in order to be most useful.

The final taxonomy was named *Interaction’s size/type* (see figure 2) and it was brought together through a simple redesign of taxonomy 1. It was realized that categories “*to sense*” and “*to handle*”, of taxonomy 1, referred to the micro interactions of taxonomy 4. The other 10 categories of taxonomy 1 referred to macro interactions.

Figure 2 – Final Taxonomy: Interaction’s Type/Size

Final Discussion and Conclusions

In this paper, we presented the first 3 iterative phases of the development of a tool to aid participants and researchers in the assessment of interaction episodes carried out through time.

Through three phases of exploration the following insights were gained about how to report interactions: (1) insights on the structure of how people report interactions, (2) a set of potentially useful action verbs, and (3) a taxonomy of types and sizes of interactions. This taxonomy is envisioned to inform participants about interaction episodes that should be reported.

These data are expected to be useful to the next steps of the development of the Experience Interaction Tool.

The tool is envisioned to aid researchers in the assessment of interactions that lead to/are followed by product experiences, particularly those that are enduring. The next steps to the development of the tool involve performing explorative studies to define how the tool will be presented to participants in research and the validation of the tool. The tool is envisioned to have two facets: it should demonstrate the types of interactions to be reported by participants and it should compel participants to report interaction stories following the structure of report resulted from this paper.

The taxonomy of 12 types of actions/interactions that are carried out in two levels in interaction episodes, that resulted from this study, supports a definition of the scope of interactions that leads to/ follows enduring product experiences.

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